
FLOOD VULNERABILITY ANALYSIS IN ELEYELE DAM AND ITS CATCHMENT AREA, IDO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, OYO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study assesses flood disaster in Eleyele Ibadan, Nigeria. The data for this study were collected from two major sources namely: primary and secondary sources. Primary data was obtained from a field survey which includes personal observations and questionnaire, etc. The secondary data was obtained from relevant textbooks, journals, periodicals; published and unpublished works, maps, internet materials and other information. The study population for this study was selected from household who have been feeling the impact of flood in Eleyele, Ibadan, Oyo state. Two hundred (200) questionnaires were administered randomly to selected residents' feeling the impact of flooding that are between 50 meters of the river to the houses. Data obtained were analyzed using descriptive statistics through frequency and percentage. Findings of this study revealed that, 94 respondents representing 47% are owner occupied while 106 respondents representing 53% are tenancy. Furthermore from findings, it also revealed heavy rainfall as the highest with 82 respondents representing 41% of the causes of flooding in the study area with land use as the least with 9 respondents representing 4.5%. This study concluded that, management of flood hazard can be as effective if, government and other stakeholders take adequate control measures related to environmental monitoring, control and protection of people and properties, and community participation in environmental monitoring and control as they show up and address them instantly.

Keywords: Causes, Effects, Household, Analysis, control measures

Introduction:

Floods are defined as extremely high flows of river, whereby water inundates flood plains or terrains outside the water-confined major river channels. Flood hazard is measured by possibility of occurrence of their damaging consequences, conceived generally as flood risk, or by their impact on society, conceived usually as the loss of lives and material damage to society (Henry, 2006). Flooding is one of the major environmental crises one has to contend with globally (Yoade et al., 2020). Rivers overflow for reasons like excessive rainfall dumping of refuse in streams and rivers (Yoade et al., 2020). The continuous unstoppable rapid urbanization, particularly in developing countries (Wong, 2015), and poorly managed urban growth and land use, coupled with destructive effects of climate change, have been the dominant cause of natural and man-induced disasters such as earthquakes, cyclones, landslides, sea-level rise, tsunami, flooding and erosion among others (Hardoy, Mitlin & Satterthwaite 2013; Mitlin & Satterthwaite 2013). In African cities, hydro-meteorological hazards, including floods and droughts, are regarded as the most common of all hazards (Niekerk & Wisner 2014). Flood vulnerability involves elements at risk such as the residents of a flood-prone area, a built environment or an ecosystem exposed to flood risk (Merz et al. 2007).

With growing evidence on cities' flood vulnerability; most flood-related disasters are not primarily caused by natural disasters. Many scholars acknowledge that the primary determinant factors are largely attributed to human activities that involve socio-political, historical and cultural relations (Birkmann 2007; Milly et al. 2002; Seyoum et al. 2011; Vojinović 2015; Vojinović & Abbott 2012). Any city with a very low quality of basic infrastructure, unplanned growth and rapid urbanization coupled with the effects of climate change means heavy rainfall can manifest as a catastrophic flood (Baker 2012; Global Footprint Network 2012). In recent years, the frequency and intensity of rainfall events, flash floods, acute riverine and coastal flooding have been on the increase, corresponding with more reported cases of flood disasters across the world (Vojinović 2015). It is highly important to focus on proactive measures rather than common focus on responding to the disaster. In line with Hyogo framework for action (HFA) guidelines (UNISDR 2005), even the recently adopted Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (SFDRR) (Kelman 2015).

Studies in Nigeria have shown that serious flood disasters have occurred in Ibadan 1985, 1987, 1990, 2011, 2015, 2016, 2017; Osogbo 1992, 1996, 2002, 2011, 2015, 2016, 2017; Yobe in 2000; Akure 1978, 1996, 2000, 2002, 2004 and 2006; and Lagos 2010, 2011, 2012, 2016, 2017; Kwara State 1991, 1992, 1993, 1994, 1997, 2001, 2002, 2003, 2004, 2005, 2006, 2007, 2008; Sokoto 2010; and other parts of the country, has shown that flooding is a major environmental phenomenon in Nigeria (Olajuyigbe, Rotowa and Durojaye, 2012; Jimoh and Iroye, 2011; Olorunfemi and Raheem, 2013; Aladelokun and Ajayi, 2014; Akukwe, 2014) with Coastal cities like Lagos, Port Harcourt, Calabar, Uyo, Warri among others have severally experienced incidences that have claimed many lives and properties worth millions of dollar (Olajuyigbe, Rotowa and Durojaye, 2012).

Materials and Methods:

Study Area

Eleyele River is situated within Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, lying within latitude 7°26'23.9"N and longitude 3°51'36.7"E. The Eleyele area is characterized by both high-density residential and commercial zones, including markets, schools, hospitals, and various public amenities.

This area, like much of Ibadan, has undergone significant urbanization over the past few decades. The river itself is a critical waterway that traverses through the city, influencing local hydrology and serving as a vital resource for various activities, including domestic use and irrigation. Eleyele Dam, built on the river, provides water for the city and helps in flood control. However, the region is prone to flooding, particularly during the rainy season, due to a combination of factors including inadequate drainage infrastructure, deforestation, and unplanned urban expansion.

Methods of assessment of flooding in the study area

The data for this study were collected from two major sources namely: primary and secondary sources. Primary data was obtained from a field survey which includes personal observations and questionnaire, etc. The questionnaire will be designed to collect data on issues related to flood related activities in the various areas, characteristics of buildings, and their level of satisfaction with flood and other information considered necessary in attaining the objectives of the research. The secondary data was obtained from relevant textbooks, journals, periodicals; published and unpublished works, maps, internet materials and other information. Maps and photographs will be used for this research. The study population for this study was the buildings within Eleyele, Ibadan, Oyo state. The sample frame refers to the study area population within which the sample will be chosen. The scope of the study area is expected to cover Eleyele environment in Ibadan city.

The choice of sample size was influenced by the need to actually target those who have been feeling the impact of flood in the area. This is so as to get enough input from each section of the town as almost all areas of the work are vulnerable to one form of flooding or another. The sampling technique that was adopted by this research is purposive and stratified sampling techniques. The questionnaire was administered using purposive sampling to the buildings within fifty (50) meters of the river network at ten (10) houses intervals. This ensured that the questionnaire was carefully administered to the target population, so as to get a better input in evaluating the effects of floods. Data collected were analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistical tool through descriptive statistics through frequency and percentage based on the set objectives.

Results

Analysis and Discussions

Socio-Economic Background of the Respondents in the Study Area

The gender distribution of the respondents is contained in table 1. The findings from Table 1 revealed that, one hundred and nine (109) are male representing 54.5%, while ninety-one (91) of the respondents are female at 45.5%. Findings revealed the age distribution of respondents. Twenty-nine (29) respondents representing 14.5% are within the age of 18-30 years, then forty-eight (48) respondents representing 24% are within the age of 31-40 years, while fifty-five (55) respondents representing 27.5% are within the age of 41-50 years, while sixty-eight (68) respondents representing 34% are within the age range of above 50. The result of marital status revealed that, seventy-one (71) respondents representing 35.5% are single then one hundred and fifteen (115) respondents representing 57.5% are married while four (4) respondents representing 2% are divorced, then six (6) respondent representing 3% are widow/widower while four (4) respondent representing 2% are separated which makes the married the most frequent in the field.

However, the result on educational qualification of residents as presented in Table 1 showed that, eleven (11) respondents representing 5.5% has no formal education, nine (9) respondent representing 4.5% level of education is primary, seventy-nine (79) respondents representing 39.5% level of education is secondary, while one hundred and one (101) respondents representing 50.5% level of education is tertiary which shows that most of the respondents level of education is tertiary. Moreover, the result of the resident's occupations revealed that, twenty-nine (29) respondents representing 14.5% are students, while twenty-one (21) respondents representing 10.5% are employed.

While ninety-six (96) respondents representing 48% are self employed then eleven (11) respondents representing 5.5% are unemployed, while forty-three (43) respondents representing 21.5% are others. Findings from the houses occupied by respondents revealed that, forty-two (42) respondents representing 21% lives in room apartment, one hundred and eighteen (118) respondents representing 59% live in flat, twenty-three (23) respondents representing 11.5% lives in bungalow while seventeen (17) respondents representing 8.5% live in duplex. This shows that majority of the respondent live in flat. Findings of status of ownership of residents in the study area revealed that ninety-four (94) respondents representing 47% are owner occupied while one hundred and six (106) respondents representing 53% are tenancy. This shows that majority of the respondent are tenants.

Respondents' duration of stay in the study area was categorized into four namely; those that have spent 0-5 years with one hundred and twenty-one (121) respondents representing 60.5%, those that have spent 5-10 years with fifty-nine (59) respondents representing 29.5%, those that have spent 10-15 years with eleven (11) respondents representing 5.5%, and those that have spent 20 years and above with nine (9) respondents representing 4.5% in the study area. The findings in table 1 revealed that forty-five (45) representing 22.5% of the respondents earned below #20,000 income, while sixty-two (62) respondents representing 31% are within the range of #20,000-#50,000 income, seventy-one (71) respondents representing 35.5% are within the range of #50,000-#80,000 income, and twenty-two (22) respondents representing 11% earned above #80,000 income. The findings from this study are similar to the results of the research conducted by Yoade et al. (2020).

Table 1: Socio-economic Characteristics of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Houses Occupied	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	109	54.5	A room apartment	42	21
Female	91	45.5	Flat	118	59
Age			Bungalow	23	11.5
18 – 30 years	29	14.5	Duplex	17	8.5
31 – 40 years	48	24	House ownership		
41 – 50 years	55	27.5	Owner	94	47
50 years and Above	68	34	Tenant	106	53
Marital Status			Duration of stay		
Single	71	35.5	0-5 years	121	60.5
Married	115	57.5	10-15years	59	29.5
Divorced	4	2	15-20years	11	5.5
Widow/Widower	6	3	20years and above	9	4.5
Separated	4	2	Income		
Academic Qualifications			Below #20,000	45	22.5
Primary	9	4.5	#20,000 – #50,000	62	31
Secondary	79	39.5	#50,000 – #80,000	71	35.5
Tertiary	101	50.5	#80,000 and above	22	11
No formal school	11	5.5			
Occupation					
Student	29	14.5			
Employed	21	10.5			
Self employed	96	48			
Unemployed	11	5.5			
Others	43	21.5			

Residents Perception on the Physical/Building Characteristics of Flood Prone Area(s)

This analyses and interpreted data collected on the residents physical characteristics based on building use which was categorized into; residential, commercial, educational, public and industrial and land acquisition categorized into; gifted, purchased and inherited in the study area, Findings showed that 132 respondents representing 66% use of building for residential, then 8 respondents representing 4.0% use of building is for commercial, then 36 respondents representing 18% use of building for educational, then 18 respondent representing 9% use of building is public use, while 6 respondents representing 3% use of building is public. Therefore the major use of buildings in the study area is mainly for residential. However, the findings of land acquisition of respondents revealed that 158 respondents representing 79% purchased their land while 34 respondents representing 17% inherited their land while 8 respondents representing 4% acquired their land through gift. Therefore, majority acquires their land by purchasing (Table 2) and the findings from this study are similar to the results of the research conducted by Yoade et al. (2020).

Table 2: Respondents' Use of Buildings and Land Acquisition

Use of Building	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Residential	132	66
Commercial	8	4
Education	36	18
Public	18	9
Industrial	6	3
Land Acquisition		
Gifted	8	4
Purchased	158	79
Inherited	34	17

Opinion of Residents' on when Flood Occurrence is usually High

Findings from the respondents' opinion on when flood occurrence usually high as revealed in table 3 shows that, flood occurrence is usually not seen from January to May and started occurring from June and high majorly from July and low from October to December as dry season commenced in the study area.

Table 3: Respondents Opinion of When Flood Occurrence is Usually High

Month	Frequency of respondent's	Percentage (%)
January	0	0.0
February	0	0.0
March	0	0.0
April	0	0.0
May	1	0.5
June	18	9
July	99	49.5
August	54	27
September	23	11.5
October	4	2
November	1	0.5
December	0	0.0
Total	200	100

Perception of Residents' on Impact of Flooding in the Study Area

The findings from the analyses by respondents on impact of flooding in the study area revealed loss of life has the highest with eighty-nine (89) responses representing 44.5%. However, eight (8) respondents representing 4% perceived loss of top soil being as the least that possible solution in the study areas (Table 4). The result on the impact is similar to the findings by Yoade et al. (2020)

Table 4: Impact of flooding in the study area

Impact	Frequency of responses	Percentage (%)
Loss of life	89	44.5
Loss of property	50	25
Loss of farmland	23	11.5
Building collapse	30	15
Loss of top soil	8	4
Total	200	100

Causes of Flooding in the Study Area

This research revealed three (3) main of all the causes of flooding in the study area which are; heavy rainfall, poor river channel and dumping of waste and refuse. The findings from the respondents' opinion revealed heavy rainfall as the highest cause of flooding in the study area and as it accounted for 82 respondents representing (41%). Elevation of the area being the least cause of flooding in the study area as it accounted for 5 respondents representing 2.5% (Table 5).

Table 5: Response to Causes of Flooding in the study area

Causes	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Distance to the river/poor river channel	44	22
Heavy Rainfall	82	41
Elevation	5	2.5
Drainage	12	6
Land Use	9	4.5
Climate change	16	8
Inadequate dumping of Waste/refuse disposal	32	16
Total	200	100

Efforts made by Government

From table 6 below, it revealed that government has made provision for waste/refuse disposal being the highest of amongst the efforts made with 86 respondents representing 43%. Moreover, construction of drainages is the least government effort towards minimizing flooding with 28 respondents representing 14%. Other efforts made by government are; construction of canals representing 26%, public enlightenment program representing 17% is also viewed also as part of government efforts minimizing flooding in the study (Table 6).

Table 6: Governments Efforts in tackling flooding

Government efforts	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Construction of canals	52	26
Provision of adequate waste/refuse disposal	86	43
Public enlightenment program	34	17
Construction of drainages	28	14
Total	200	100

Community Participation to Flooding

Findings from community participation to flooding revealed removal of waste from water ways as the highest with eighty-seven (87) representing 43.5%. However, construction of drainages represents 8.5% being the least of the community participation towards minimizing flooding in the study area (Table 7).

Table 7: Community Participation to flooding in the study area

Participation	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Removal of waste from water ways	87	43.5
Filling of dilapidated road	55	27.5
Provision of waste disposal facilities	41	20.5
Construction of drainage	17	8.5
Total	200	100

Opinion of Respondents on Possible Solutions to Flooding

Of all the possible solutions, the least was planting of trees (afforestation) with eighteen (18) responses representing 9%. The most considered of all the possible solutions to flooding was sanitation on removal of waste from drainage with sixty-seven (67) responses representing 33.5%. Other possible solutions included which the residents feel government should do are; river/water ways and drainage expansion, provision of adequate waste disposal and construction of canals in the study area (Table 8).

Table 8: Respondent's Opinion on Possible Solutions to Flooding

Possible Solutions	Frequency of respondents	Percentage (%)
River/water ways and drainage expansion	38	19
Planting of trees (Afforestation)	18	9
Provision of adequate waste disposal	45	22.5
Sanitation on removal of waste from drainage	67	33.5
Construction of canals	32	16
Total	200	100

Conclusion and Recommendations

The threat posed by flooding in Eleyele and its catchment area(s) in Ibadan has been highlighted in this study. The findings from this research revealed the magnitude of the event of flood hazard in the study area with heavy rainfall during the rainy season being the major as it as well make the Eleyele dam to overflow it boundary and running through other river tributaries. Although, other causes of flooding to the study area are presented such as poor river channel, elevation, drainage, land use, climate change and inadequate dumping of waste/refuse. This research has presented a useful tool that would help government, concerned stakeholders and Nongovernmental Organizations (NGOs) in planning towards flood management and control in the study area. Moreover, the findings from this research require more information for a complete assessment and evaluation of flood risk. This study further recommends; public education/enlightenment program on climate change, flood hazards and best response approach; compliance based on the guidelines on the encroachment from land use planning and policies and development to the flood plains area(s) especially along the river as well as its tributaries in the study area; construction of flood control structures and cleared the existing ones that are blocking waste/refuse at a high flood vulnerable areas; new standard of setback be set on major streams and rivers due to increase in population and enforce environmental laws and regulations to prevent indiscriminate dumping of refuse and wastes in unauthorized locations.

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